

Renewal Plan for the Old Part of Chittagong: A Case Study of Firingi Bazar

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Abstract—Due to rapid pressured of population growth, city has started to lose its old tradition. City becomes congested with uncomfortably living. Urban renewal refers orderly development of settlements as well as land redevelopment. For this paper Chittagong city has been selected as study area. It had a great tradition but it has been losing its concord. Land use pattern of this place is also haphazard due to lack of planning intervention. Renewal plan is needed to ascertain suitable redevelopment and to recommend on preservation of city heritage structure. The goal of this study is to prepare a renewal plan using local planning approach. Social impact methods have been used to achieve this goal. Both primary and secondary data are used to achieve the goal. This study may find out a complete solution for healthy living in old Part of city. This study will help to preserve its tradition and makes urban lives more livable.

Keywords—Renewal Plan, Social Impact

I. INTRODUCTION

THE urban renewal of centers is about building on the strengths of each place, transforming under-used or dilapidated areas, boosting local economies and providing a mix of uses and activities, which meet the needs of the community [3]. Urban renewal is a program of land redevelopment in areas of moderate to high-density urban land use. Renewal has had both successes and failures. Its modern incarnation began in the late 19th century in developed nations and experienced an intense phase in the late 1940s – under the rubric of reconstruction. The process has had a major impact on many urban landscapes, and has played an important role in the history and demographics of cities around the world. Urban renewal may involve relocation of businesses, the demolition of structures, the relocation of people, and the use of eminent domain (government purchase of property for public purpose) as a legal instrument to take private property for city-initiated development projects. In some cases, renewal may result in urban sprawl and less congestion when areas of cities receive freeways and express ways. Urban renewal has been seen by proponents as an economic engine and a reform mechanism and by critics as a mechanism for control [5]. It may enhance existing communities, and in some cases result in the demolition of neighborhoods. Many cities link the revitalization of the central business district and gentrification

of residential neighborhoods to earlier urban renewal programs. Over time, urban renewal evolved into a policy based less on destruction and more on renovation and investment, and today is an integral part of many local governments, often combined with small and big business incentives. Firingi Bazar is historically renowned for commercial activities. Actually, it has been providing a great role in representing Chittagong as an efficient commercial city. Chittagong has a multicultural heritage of Islamic, Hindu and Buddhist traditions. Modern Chittagong developed in the 20th century under British colonial role. Today, Chittagong is one of the fastest growing cities in the world. A major commercial and industrial center, the city also has a globally competitive special economic zone. With the Port of Chittagong being expanded and developed, regional neighbors of Bangladesh have eyed Chittagong as a future regional transit hub. The port city is seen as crucial to the economic development of landlocked southern Asia including Northeast India, Bhutan, Nepal and parts of Southern China and Burma [2].

II. METHODOLOGY

Firingi Bazar is in the south zone of Chittagong city is selected as study area. It is of ward no. 33. This is beside the river Karnafuli. The total area is about 0.551526 sq. km. The educational status of this area is good. Male literacy rate is more than that of female. It is located in latitude & longitude; 22°21'N 91°50'E. It is actually a highly dense area. Approximately 26620 people live here [1]. The objective of the study is to analyze the existing condition and propose a suitable land use pattern in old part of Chittagong city (Firingi Bazar). To achieve the research objective both primary and secondary data are used. The number of buildings, business centers, recreational places, residential areas etc. were easily located or identified by the surveyor. Secondary data were collected from Chittagong Development Authority (CDA). After collecting data, the educational prospect, commercial view, residential state, population situation, road circulation, educational point of view etc. are thoroughly analyzed by having some definite process or method. Having analyzed the data, lacking and the existing venerable condition must be located. It actually fixes up which areas have to be reformed and redeveloped. Having analyzed the data, lacking and the existing venerable condition must be located. It actually fixes up which area has to be reformed and redeveloped. Finally, a concerned plan or proposal on the basis of existing problems and benefits is been prepared.

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III. DIMENSIONS OF URBAN RENEWAL

Different definitions are given by planners, academicians and researchers aim at sustainability by integrating the different dimensions of urban renewal. These are:

- a. Physical renewal leads to improvement of urban fabric;
- b. Social renewal leads to improvement of community and housing;
- c. Cultural renewal promotes enhancement of culture and traditions;
- d. Economic renewal leads to new generation of employment and revenue; and
- e. Environmental renewal leads to minimizing ecological imbalances in urban environment [4].

IV. APPROACHES TO URBAN RENEWAL

Renewal plan is the plan by which a dead city or a collapse area can retain its dynamicity [6]. Over a period of time a renewal plan must be brought for an area because with the changing of time a big change come into the functions of the city. Besides this an actual redevelopment plan must be carried for the area. Indeed, provide the plan is soundly based, its execution can and may often be a combination of small measure, individual schemes and large scale “comprehensive” developments. Each of these may have its proper place and small scheme, the “face-lift”, or an individual traffic management measures can make a useful combination. The three activities, which are very important for the renewal plan, are given below.

Preservation is the stage of a renewal plan in which the important features, important historical buildings etc. are preserved. It is very important because sometimes these show the traditional history of the city or area. This “preservation” stage is applied for the Renewal Plan of Firingi Bazaar Area. In this area different types of buildings or places should be preserved such as Baponibitan, Bangladesh Bank, Hotel Shajahan, and Hotel Raj etc. Besides these the Mazars (religious place), General Post Office (service building) are also preserved [3]

The commercial buildings are preserved because these are very old and important buildings in this area. These reflect the traditional variety of the area. The religious features were preserved because it is very important to preserve the religious background of the area. In this area the main attraction is the wood storage shops. Huge numbers of wood shop are in this area. Actually, it is the tradition of this area. These shops are preserved in an organized way.

Improvement is taken to mean the process by which existing building features or areas are brought back into worthwhile state after they had become outdated and unsatisfactory [7]. This method is applied in this area which are not yet dead and which are therefore not rise for redevelopment but which have become out-of-date and ill maintained and which show every sign of gating more and more dismal and depress. The road condition of this area is not so good. Firstly, the width of the road was not sufficient for this area. As time progresses, the vehicular movement have

become more and more. But the width of the road is still same. There is no planned relation between the residential, commercial, services and other types of area. In proposed renewal plan these area are placed in definite places.

It is taken to mean the process, which involves clearance of property and buildings of new structures according to a definite preconceived plan with a layout different form that of the area before redevelopment was under taken. It implies a comprehensive plan over a substantial area and is part of an overall plan; otherwise, the process is mere rebuilding. Redevlopments extend in scale from the individual rebuilding of a single property to the comprehensive redevelopment of the whole town center, and the planning problems it presents are equally varied.

V. ANALYSIS

A. Building

From the existing situation of “Firingi bazar”, we can easily acknowledge that this area was decorated in thoughts of earlier period for a definite number of population, land use, residential use, commercial use etc. However, as time passes through the condition appears so obstructed due to the present growth of developments, population, and communications sectors etc. So an urban renewal plan is badly needed for this area very firmly. The urban renewal plan for this area must be a sustainable plan. It should contain goals, objectives, preservation, redevelopment where the communication facilities, commercial values, residential aspects, recreational places etc. are to be proposed. For those deeds some existing data’s must be gathered.

The buildings of the area are in dilapidated condition. A large portion of the total houses are semi-Pacca (41%). Houses of tin shed are not small in amount (19%). The rest are Pacca house. As the area was famous for its trade activities, a large number of houses were used for the labors related with the trade works. Moreover there were factories of dry fish which were Kacha or semi-Pacca. These buildings were suitable to be Kacha and semi-Pacca.

In the study area there is no building of above 7 stories. Most of the buildings are of one storied. However, with the growth of the population the stories of the buildings should be increased to support the increased population. More than thousand buildings are one storied Depending on these data a bar chart is given below. From the chart the relation among the height of the buildings can easily find out. The largest portion of the buildings are residential that are of 1000 in number. Some commercial buildings also prevail here. These commercial buildings are thought to be the heart of the region. Educational buildings are too much small in number. Therefore, buildings of this purpose should be increased in proportion to the students of this area.

B. Existing Land Use Pattern of Firingi Bazaar

The building types of the Firingi Bazaar area have no regularity in building size, shape, design and construction. It often creates not only the visual non-conformity but also

hampers development management; creates obstacle in supply of materials this area. That is why the format of the building should be regularized by taking proper plan. A proper harmony should be maintained in the whole area that should represent the area specifically. All semi pacca building must be pacca and slum area should be tin shaded. There is no similarity in building height. This often creates problem in height zoning. That is why adequate amount of light and air flow are strongly prohibited. It is responsible for creating traffic jam and compactness in the total area also. The basic sectors of land use of the locality are placed randomly having no planning thoughts. That is why sometimes it is seen that

1. All people are not having basic facilities like educational, commercial etc. equally
2. Traffic jam is being held continuously.
3. Congestion is taking place in this area.
4. Proper distribution of goods is being hampered.
5. Unplanned developments are being placed.
6. Drainage systems are getting poorer.
7. Wrong settlements are being held.

Though it is one of the major junctions of drainage system in Chittagong city the entire drainage systems are not sustainable due to misuse of the drains. This often occurs by throwing garbage here and there, inadequate sedimentation and proper management. It also occurs when the river flow are spoiled. In the recent time the port authority of Chittagong city has taken a decision of dropping containers in the river banks of Firingi Bazaar. As it is already been located in port area, there is no necessity of placing it there. It may cause a lot of difficulties like,

1. The buildup area can be hampered by the over wastages of container.
2. The beautiful river sites can be dispersed.
3. The natural system of river flow can be hampered.
4. River area can be over packed.

Total number of population in the area is increasing day by day. There is not any projection of population size for different services. As a consequence the people of the area are suffering from lack of different utility services.

VI. PROPOSAL FOR THE RENEWAL PLAN OF THE AREA

The critical analysis of the study area promotes us to the proper way to take the future plan so as to recover present problems and sufferings. Thus some significant proposals are to be considered for Firingi bazar area. The proposals are given below:

1. **Make a suitable zoning based land use system:** In this study area no zoning sense is staying. For this reason a certain zoning should be introduced.
2. **Give sustainable settlement for the slum inhabitants:** As poor people live randomly here and there in the locality they must be located in a definite area.
3. **Dredge up the river in order to remove natural sedimentation of the river Karnafulli:** For the over filling of the bank of this river a proper widens drainage system should be allocated as well as sedimentation must be prohibited.

4. **Redevelop the fish storage:** The existing fishing storage is functioned with so many problems like drainage, shipping, communication etc. So it should be formulated with proper functioning due to make it more meaningful according to the locality.
5. **Establish a Public Park and Pathway beside the river:** In order to remove the monotonous mentalities of the inhabitants and establishing the golden beauty of the river a perfect pathway and a recreational park must be located.
6. **Change the direction of the biggest drain in this area:** The direction of the drainage system must be changed to protect the park and pathway as well as the fishing storage center from the odder pollution.
7. **Protect the river bank area from the port authority:** As the river bank area is being undertaken, it can do hamper the residential area, park, pathway etc. So the container drop age should be dispersed from the area.
8. **Fabrication of a proper height zoning in the locality:** As the existing area are not done with proper height zone the residential and the important building should zone not only with proper height zone but also in proper placing. This can formulate the natural beauty of the area as well as make the meaningful zoning.

VII. FINDING

Every research work has its particular findings. Findings of this study can be differentiated from each other. A regulated land use has been proposed for this area. Besides these findings, the directions of the main drain try to be changed from the center part of this area. By this way, the area can be protected from bad odor. It will be a safe way of emitting the wastage without much pollution. A good road network has been proposed. A proposed new road, which will be connected with Shah Amanat Bridge and Sodorghat area, can be a great achievement to the acceleration of the commercial activities. For the lack of a good management, an area can be made unsuitable for living. If this happened, the people of the area will migrant another area for better facilities. This can make a very bad impact upon the whole city. Firingi Bazaar area can be regarded as this type of condition. This area is very old and important area in Chittagong. The road network of this is change and it is given such type of figure by which a good circulation can be ensured. The buildings of this area are very congested. No planning is maintained to build the building. For the dynamicity, the area should be divided according to zoning concept. By this way, the privacy of each area can be preserved. There is no recreational place in this area.

VIII. CONCLUSION

It is obvious that the existing condition of Firingi bazar is near to be demolished in case of its sustainability. Therefore, it is a burning question to fabricate a proper urban renewal plan for this ward. However, in case of performing the condition few difficulties may arise in front of us. However, avoiding some difficulties a proper renewal plan can be performed

which will contain a great impact in commercial, residential, communicational and educational as well as in formulating a harmonic human settlement. The drainage and dredging of riverside is also a vital topic. That is why following the other reference and proper management a renewal plan must be held to enrich and enlighten its legendary aspect. The population projection is also one kind of important term which will tell us about the future growth and development of any area. The proposed plan is done by thinking the future population where it will be more applicable. The present step that is taken by the Government to make a sub road for the loaded and heavy vehicles is also very praiseworthy. It will reduce the traffic jam very firmly. In fine we can say that the proposed plan has been done in the order of present condition which is really very venerable. The Government and public participation is badly needed to implement this sort of plan. Besides this proper budgeting and financial distribution must also be done. Areas that are needed to be readjusted and exploited must also be correctly organized for the welfare of the locality.

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